

Pathways to Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: the SHAPE-ID Toolkit

Find tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Evaluating Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research

Abstract

This guide illustrates why evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research requires particular expertise.

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Online source – SHAPE-ID Toolkit

This publication is an extract of the SHAPE-ID Toolkit. For a general overview, visit: [10.5281/zenodo.4743703](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743703).

The Toolkit provides tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Evaluating ID and TD requires particular expertise

Introduction

Experts who evaluate ID and TD projects must be able to see its specific qualities. Experts develop this skill by deeply engaging with ID and TD, either practically or theoretically. Panels which evaluate ID and TD projects need to include this expertise in decision making.

Keywords

Expertise in ID and TD, quality of ID and TD, specific challenges of ID and TD

Summary

People who assess ID and TD projects—for instance to substantiate funding decisions—must be able to see its qualities. Having carried out many such projects does not necessarily qualify for this, in the same way that drinking a lot of wine does not qualify you as a wine expert. Rather such experts are people who have deeply engaged with ID and TD, either by practically exploring various ways to address key challenges or by analysing and conceptualising ID and TD. Through this engagement experts become aware of different understandings of ID and TD, typical challenges and ways to address them. Building on this knowledge they can assess a project's quality, e.g. by answering questions like:

- ▶ Do the applicants explain what they mean by ID and TD? Is this understanding in line with the mix of disciplines and societal actors and adequate to the aims of the project?
- ▶ Are there concepts to understand and methods to address key challenges of ID and TD, such as joint problem framing, integration or having impact? Are these concepts and methods state of the art. Are they suitable for the composition of the team and the issue addressed?
- ▶ Is substantial time and budget reserved for exchange and mutual learning? Is there room to reflect on the consequences of this exchange and can the project be adapted if needed?

Panels which evaluate ID and TD projects need to include this expertise in decision making. One possibility is a mixed panel of experts from different disciplines, sectors of society and specialist in ID and TD. Another is to include ID and TD specialists in the review process. However, they are designed, such evaluations:

- ▶ must include experts who are able to see the particular qualities of ID and TD and who know the state of art in ID and TD;
- ▶ should include them more fully in the decision-making body, relative to the weight that is put on ID and TD.

Further Resources

- ▶ Brian Belcher's webpage: <https://researcheffectiveness.ca/resources/>
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https://www.academia.edu/3758572/Evaluating_Research_beyond_Scientific_Impact_How_to_Include_Criteria_for_Productive_Interactions_and_Impact_on_Practice_and_Society

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